

ADAPTATIONS OF CHAUGARKHA GOATS TO THE HIMALAYAN ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

The Chaugarkha goat, the second registered goat breed from Uttarakhand after the Pantja breed, is primarily reared for meat production. Found mainly in Kumaon region, this small-sized breed is well-adapted to the semi-temperate conditions of the Central Himalayan ecosystem. It thrives on rugged terrains where other agricultural activities are limited, owing to its hard hooves and sure-footed agility. Farmers rear these goats in a semi-feral system, relying on natural forage with minimal supplemental feeding. Chaugarkha goats significantly contribute to rural livelihoods through meat production mainly. The breed is low-maintenance, disease-resistant, and economically viable for small-scale farmers. Farmers mainly use Banj oak (*Quercus leucotrichophora*) as a fodder source due to its abundance, despite its lower nutritional value. Conservation efforts are crucial to protect this indigenous breed from crossbreeding, habitat loss, and changing farming practices. Government and research initiatives, including selective breeding and the National Livestock Mission, aim to sustain and improve Chaugarkha goat farming, ensuring economic stability and biodiversity conservation in Uttarakhand.

KEYWORDS: Banj, Chaugarkha, farmers, goats, Uttarakhand

INTRODUCTION

The Chaugarkha goat (INDIA_GOAT_2400_CHAUGARKHA_06040) is the second registered goat breed from Uttarakhand (NBAGR, 2024) after the Pantja breed (Verma *et al.*, 2008). It is a small-sized breed reared primarily for meat production, with a coat color that varies between black, fawn, and white. Found mainly in the Almora district and the adjoining areas of Bageshwar, Pithoragarh, and Nainital, this breed is well-adapted to the semi-temperate conditions of the Central Himalayan ecosystem (Gandhi, 2015). Chaugarkha goats are known for their hardiness, thriving on denuded cliffs where other agricultural activities are barely profitable. Their hooves are hard and well-adapted to rocky and uneven surfaces, providing them with excellent grip and stability. This adaptation makes them sure-footed and agile, allowing them to navigate steep slopes with ease. Their ability to maintain balance on rugged terrain helps them access food sources in challenging environments while minimizing the risk of injury (Jana *et al.*, 2020). The breed follows an unorganized, semi-feral husbandry system, with an average herd size ranging from 5 to 30 goats. This breed commonly exhibited three hair coat colors: white, black, and fawn (Singh and Barwal, 2009). A characteristic facial stripe running from the base of the horn to the nose was common, along with a convex head and small to medium-sized pendulous ears (10–16 cm) that curved slightly upward at the tip (Jana *et al.*, 2020). At full-mouth age, males weigh around 18.18 kg, while females weigh 17.61 kg. The goat kid once a year, typically giving birth to one or two kids (Chauhan *et al.*, 2021). They have a small udder with well-set, pointed teats. At night, these goats are generally housed

alongside other livestock, reflecting their close integration into the traditional pastoral lifestyle of the region (Singh and Barwal, 2007).

One of the primary ways Chaugarkha goats benefit farmers is through milk and meat production. Goat milk is highly valued for its medicinal properties. Additionally, Chaugarkha goats have a good growth rate, making them suitable for meat production, which is a significant source of revenue for farmers. Their meat is coarse and devoid of fat (Ganie *et al.*, 2017). Apart from direct income from milk and meat, these goats also contribute to sustainable farming practices. Their manure is an excellent organic fertilizer, improving soil fertility and enhancing agricultural productivity. This reduces farmers' dependency on chemical fertilizers, leading to cost savings and better crop yields (Jitendra *et al.*, 2016).

Chaugarkha goats are relatively low-maintenance and require minimal investment in housing and feed, making them an affordable and profitable livestock option. Chaugarkha goats in Uttarakhand are typically reared in an unorganized, semi-feral system, where they are taken to nearby hilly terrains for browsing (Singh and Barwal, 2007). Throughout the year, they rely primarily on natural forage, with little to no supplemental feed. Kids are raised on their mothers' milk, along with tree leaves and local grasses. Farmers traditionally take their livestock, including goats, sheep, cattle, and buffalo, to the nearby forest for browsing and grazing early in the morning, bringing them back to sheds in the evening. Bucks are generally kept for random mating and later sold for meat, contributing to the local economy. In Uttarakhand, farmers mainly use to feed Banj oak (*Quercus leucotrichophora*) as fodder due to its abundance, though they rank it lower than Moru and Kharsu oak in nutritional and milk production value (Arya *et al.*, 2011). A survey in the Garhwal region confirmed that while Banj oak is widely used, it is a lower-quality fodder, primarily fed during scarcity (Barman and Rai, 2008). Apart from low feeding cost, these goats are highly resilient and resistant to common diseases, which reduces veterinary costs. The study on Chaugarkha goats is the third of its kind on anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) dynamics, following research on Saanen (Monniaux *et al.*, 2011) and Angora (Alkan *et al.*, 2020) breeds. Findings indicate that serum AMH concentration declines during puberty and stabilizes in adulthood, remaining unaffected by the estrous cycle or early gestation. Notably, AMH levels exhibit a moderate positive correlation with antral follicle count, ovarian surface area, ovulation rate, and litter size, highlighting its potential as a reproductive biomarker in Chaugarkha goats (Kharayat *et al.*, 2024). With government and research institutions focusing on improving the breed and promoting scientific goat farming, Chaugarkha goats are becoming a key driver of rural economic stability. By integrating goat farming with agriculture, Uttarakhand's farmers are enhancing their income, ensuring food security, and promoting sustainable livelihoods in the region.

Since these goat breeds are well-adapted to Uttarakhand's hilly terrain, disease-resistant, and thrive with minimal inputs, their conservation is vital for biodiversity and rural livelihoods. However, threats like crossbreeding, habitat loss, and changing farming practices endanger their survival. Conservation efforts focus on breed registration, selective breeding, community participation, and government support through initiatives like the National Livestock Mission.

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